

Kravchenko Larisa Anatolyevna,
Ph.D. in Economics, Associate Professor,
Associate Professor of the Department of Economic Theory,
Institute of Economics and Management,
V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University,
Simferopol, Russian Federation.

Troyan Irina Anatolyevna,
Ph.D. in Economics, Associate Professor,
Associate Professor of the Department of Economic Theory,
Institute of Economics and Management,
V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University,
Simferopol, Russian Federation.

Abibullaev Memet Serverovich,
Ph.D. in Economics, Associate Professor,
Associate Professor of the Department Finance and credit
Institute of Economics and Management,
V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University,
Simferopol, Russian Federation.

**ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN LABOR MARKET:
OPPORTUNITIES AND RISKS OF INTEGRATION**

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The article examined theoretical concepts used to analyze the role and impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on the labor market. A rationale for synthesizing micro- and macroeconomic models for integrating AI into the labor market was provided. The complexity of quantitatively and qualitatively assessing the impact of AI on the labor market was emphasized. The authors applied a SWOT analysis of the implementation of AI technologies in the labor market, systematically examining the strengths and weaknesses, as well as threats and opportunities. Global trends in labor market transformation were analyzed in terms of the spread of professions influenced by artificial intelligence. A detailed analysis of the impact of artificial intelligence on the financial sector is provided, which directly creates transformational effects on the labor market. Characteristic features of labor market development in Russia were identified, as well as key objectives for applying AI technologies, including for the production process, marketing and sales, and human capital development. In the context of leveraging the benefits and mitigating the risks of AI implementation in the labor market, key necessary areas are proposed. These include retraining and upskilling programs, promoting synergistic interactions between AI and humans, developing AI-based innovation and entrepreneurship, combating inequality and bias, ethical standards and government regulation of AI, and policies to protect workers' rights. Key areas for the development of AI technologies in the labor market were proposed. These include encouraging the widespread adoption of AI in the economy, modernizing labor market infrastructure, leveraging AI capabilities to improve job quality, scenario analysis, and practical planning.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, labor market, workforce, financial costs, financial sector, investments, innovations, technologies.

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